

The Development of a Portable, Self-Contained, and Easily Deployed Hydrophone System for Recording Deep-Ocean Ambient Noise

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Abstract - This paper presents the development of a portable, self-contained, hydrophone system which acquires and records deep-ocean ambient acoustic noise.

I. INTRODUCTION

The hydrophone system is designated as the Deep Deployable Ambient Recording System (DDARS). It was developed by the Naval Research Laboratory-Underwater Sound Reference Detachment (NRL-USRD), Orlando, Florida, and the Naval Undersea Warfare Center Division (NUWCD), Newport, Rhode Island. The DDARS is easily deployed, acquires and records two hours of deep-ocean ambient acoustic noise over a period of several hours or days, and is easily located and recovered.

This paper discusses the DDARS design requirements, engineering development, final design configuration, and test and evaluation. Data from the acoustic calibration and recorded ocean ambient noise is also presented.

II. BACKGROUND

Researchers have theorized about and made measurements of the reduced ambient noise levels present in the deep ocean as compared with surface ambient noise levels. This reduction in ambient noise provides an increase in the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The increase in SNR achievable in the 8 to 20 kHz region is a function of the water depth and the absorption of sound in sea water, α . Another phenomenon of deep-ocean ambient noise is the directionality of the noise field. This anisotropic feature can be exploited with the use of a directional receiver. The DDARS was designed and developed to exploit these phenomena.

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Current U.S. Navy undersea tracking ranges utilize frequencies in the 8 to 20 kHz region to acoustically locate range vehicles while conducting operations. Underwater vehicles are "tracked" on the range with transducers called pingers. Historically, the tracking system hydrophones, which are mounted on the sea floor in water less than 2000 m deep, have been hydrophones with cardioid directivity, and are subject to an ambient noise source generated predominantly by wind-driven waves. The noise level in the deep ocean (>4000 m) is reduced, however, as compared with this surface noise, by the absorption of sound in the sea water in this frequency band. In addition, the shape of this deep-ocean noise is anisotropic with the greatest intensity received at an angle of 0° with the vertical.

To calculate the increase in SNR, a deep-ocean hydrophone can achieve over a hydrophone close to the surface, an analytical model was created, based on wind-generated noise. Both the deep-ocean omnidirectional SNR and the increased SNR that a directional hydrophone provides is determined. The directional hydrophone has the requirements to both discriminate against the noise while allowing tracking ping detection of the range vehicles. Through this modeling effort, a 4-element line array was selected as a candidate directional hydrophone. The DDARS utilizes this vertical line array configuration.

The reduction of the deep-ocean noise ambient level received by this directional hydrophone allows less signal to be detected by the acoustic tracking pinger. Since there is less signal required, the distance between tracking sensor nodes can be extended. This means that less in-water hardware is required to provide the same tracking coverage area as previously installed omnidirectional receivers.

III. DESIGN REQUIREMENTS

The critical hydrophone array design requirements of the DDARS are given in Table I. In addition to these, critical structural requirements were imposed as a result of the need for high mechanical

reliability; the DDARS had to be easily deployed and recovered from a ship's deck, reconfigured for rapid redeployment, and withstand the trip to and from a maximum ocean depth of 5000 m. Meeting all requirements was a challenge because some requirements narrowly limited others. For example, the acoustic sensor element requirements of sensitivity as a function of frequency, capacitance, and directivity placed narrow limits on sensor element configuration, piezoelectric material, and need for pressure equalization. Several prototype acoustic sensor element configurations were evaluated extensively, both analytically and experimentally. Two striped electrode cylindrical sizes including two configurations for acoustically shielding the inside surface were evaluated. In addition, spherical elements of two diameters and two spherical shell configurations were analytically and experimentally evaluated.

Some structural requirements also had a strong impact on others. Low DDARS component weights were necessary to enable easy handling. However, these weights were driven higher by the need for high structural strength to withstand both dynamic deployment loads and hydrostatic pressure loads. Also, high in-water weight minimizes descent time. Another critical trade-off affecting weight was caused by the conflict between the buoyancy requirement for the submersible recovery buoy, in-water weights of hydrophone and electronics bottle, and expendable anchor. All of these requirements affect in-water and in-air weight, sometimes in opposing directions.

TABLE I
DDARS SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

HYDROPHONE ARRAY

Operating Bandwidth:	8 kHz - 20 kHz
Preamp Self-Noise:	≤ -170 dBV/rt-Hz
Sensor Capacitance:	≥ 850 pF
Array Sensitivity (FFVS):	≥ -195 dB re 1 V/μPa
Element Directivity:	Omnidirectional
Array Type:	4-element line array
Element Spacing:	λ/2 @ 15 kHz
Operating Pressure:	≤ 55.2 MPa (8000 psi)
Operating Temperature:	3 to 28 °C
Array Length:	61 cm

IV. DESIGN CONFIGURATION

The final DDARS system configuration is shown in Fig. 1. The system mission profile consists of a deployment by launching the buoy first, then, sequentially, the hydrophone line array with electronics housing, acoustic release, and anchor, all joined by individual 18 m braided polyester rope assemblies. After release of the anchor, the DDARS sinks to the bottom, and the hydrophone line array

is activated, acquires, and records ambient acoustic noise with a digital audio tape recorder (DAT). Subsequently, the acoustic release is triggered, separates from the anchor, and the system returns to the ocean surface for recovery.

Fig. 1. The DDARS system configuration.

A. Buoy

The DDARS buoy is cast in an oblate spheroid shape, 86 cm in major diameter, of syntactic foam. Its mass is 236 kg and it provides a positive submerged buoyancy of 1335 N (300 lb), at a maximum depth of 5000 m. Structurally, the buoy is supported by an axial steel rod with a 22250 N (5000 lb) strength, and terminated at each end with an eye nut for lifting and tethering. To provide quick location for recovery the buoy has two pockets near its top center which retain a submersible xenon strobe light beacon and a radio transmitter, both of which are activated by a pressure switch.

B. Acoustic Release

After actuation by a coded acoustic signal sent from the recovery ship, the commercially available acoustic release allows the DDARS to return to the ocean surface. The unit has a redundant acoustic sensor and release actuator, to insure a reliable release, which utilizes inconel burn wire as the release mechanism. The acoustic release has a mass of 81 kg, and a submerged weight of 431 N (97 lb).

C. Anchor

The DDARS anchor is expendable and consists of a low cost 46 cm square solid cast concrete block. Its mass is 220 kg and provides an in-water negative buoyancy of 1202 N (270 lb). Two steel eyebolts with encapsulated shanks provide attachment points for lifting and tethering the system.

D. Hydrophone Line Array and Electronics Housing

The main objectives of the structural design of the DDARS hydrophone array and electronics housing were strength and reliability. To achieve this, the pressure housing, which contains the electronics, was designed to be an integral part of the the hydrophone array support frame as shown in Fig. 2. This eliminated the need for any underwater electrical cables or connectors and increased reliability. The hydrophone array support frame was fabricated of steel drill rods with ring stiffeners joined by high strength brazing. The pressure housing was fabricated of high strength stainless steel (17-4 PH), tested to a hydrostatic pressure equivalent of 6850 m (10000 psi), and a maximum axial load of 4450 N (1000 lb). The total mass is 35 kg, and in-water weight is 254 N (57 lb).

The final design configuration for the line array consisted of four hydrophone sensor elements equally spaced 5.08 cm apart ($\lambda/2$ @ 15 kHz), immersed in dB grade castor oil for acoustic impedance matching as shown in Fig. 2. Each element is a 2.54 cm diameter sphere made from lead zirconate titanate piezoelectric ceramic, Navy Type I. A tubular neoprene boot provides an acoustic window.

Fig. 2. DDARS hydrophone array configuration.

This configuration was chosen based on the capacitance and free-field voltage sensitivity (FFVS) specification of Table I. The spherical elements are built from four quadraspheres, electrically connected in series to increase the elements FFVS by +6 dB. Each element is also designed to allow for the free-

flooding of its interior with castor oil to prevent changes in FFVS as a function of hydrostatic pressure. The final values of capacitance and FFVS for each element are 1200 pF and -189 dB re $V/\mu\text{Pa}$, respectively.

The electronic beamforming system consisted of the components shown in the block diagram of Fig. 3. The preamplifiers consisted of a single, low-noise operational amplifier which boasts a noise voltage of -170 dBV/rt-Hz @ 10 kHz. A preamplifier voltage gain of +40 dBV is provided to meet system requirements. Shading is accomplished using a summing amplifier with weighted input resistances. The output of the upper sensor element is recorded separately to provide an omnidirectional noise measurement.

A microprocessor is employed to control all data recorder timing in the system, including: 1) the delay required for the DDARS to descend to the bottom of the ocean before data acquisition began; 2) the recording length time, and; 3) the time between recording sessions. The microprocessor also developed a calibration signal for the system which was injected at the input of the preamplifiers at -60 dBV to provide a calibration of the electronics before each recording session. The calibration signal is a family of tones and was required for post processing the recorded data. Data recording is performed by a commercially available, compact, digital-audio tape (DAT) recorder.

Power is supplied to the system by several 2 V, 2.5 AH, sealed lead acid batteries electrically connected in series and parallel to from the required supply voltages.

Fig. 3. DDARS electronics block diagram.

Fig. 4. (a) Typical beam patterns of the DDARS array taken at 8 kHz in the XZ plane; (b) FFVS of the DDARS array when all four elements were electrically connected in parallel.

V. TEST AND EVALUATION

The test and evaluation of the DDARS consisted of acoustic testing of the hydrophone array and electronics at the NRL-USRD calibration facility, and at-sea testing. At-sea testing was performed at the Naval Undersea Warfare Center Detachment-Atlantic Undersea Test and Evaluation Center (NUWCD-AUTEC), Andros Island, Bahamas, and deep-ocean testing 300 km northeast of Eleuthera Island, Bahamas.

A. Acoustic Testing at NRL-USRD

Acoustic testing and calibration of the DDARS array and electronics was performed at the NRL-USRD Lake Facility and Anechoic Tank Facility (ATF). These tests consisted of FFVS and receiving beam pattern measurements under ambient conditions and as a function of temperature and hydrostatic pressure. Fig. 4a shows a typical beam pattern at 8 kHz for the line array in the XZ (vertical) plane when all four elements are electrically connected in parallel. Overall, the array behaved like a typical line array as demonstrated by beamwidths taken at various frequencies over the operating bandwidth. This was originally a matter of concern, given the nearness of the rigid, air-filled electronics housing. Fig. 4b shows the receiving response of the unshaded line array when all four elements are electrically connected in parallel. It can be seen that the FFVS for the array ranges from -189 to -191.7 dB re $V/\mu\text{Pa}$ over the operating bandwidth of 8 to 20 kHz. Finally, acoustical measurements of FFVS performed as a function of temperature and pressure showed changes of less than 2 dB, indicating that the array would perform satisfactorily at the required depth.

B. At-Sea Tests at NUWCD-AUTEC

The DDARS tests performed at NUWC-AUTEC consisted of five deployments. The reason for

tests at this site was to gain experience with the deployment and recovery of the DDARS. Two deployments were performed with the AUTEC Ocean Hauldown Facility (OHDF), shown in Fig. 5. This facility was employed by tethering the DDARS acoustic release, the hydrophone array, and buoy to the OHDF termination buoy. This enabled controlled acoustic and depth testing of the DDARS to 700 m. Two deployments were carried out at this facility, both to a depth of 275 m. For the first test, the DDARS was returned to the surface by raising the OHDF termination buoy. This allowed evaluation of deployment, recovery, and hydrophone (DAT tape and battery change-out) reconfiguration procedures. The second test was performed by releasing the DDARS from the OHDF termination buoy by triggering the acoustic release. One hour of ambient noise data was recorded during both of these tests.

The last three deployments were performed with the entire DDARS including expendable anchor to a depth of 1875 m, 16 km east of Andros Island in the Tongue of the Ocean. This deployment tested the full mission profile and resulted in the recording of six hours of ambient noise data. An example of this data is shown in Fig. 6.

C. Deep-Ocean Tests

Deep-ocean tests of the DDARS was carried out in depths of 4880 m, 300 km northeast of Eleuthera Island, Bahamas. These tests resulted in four successful deployment/retrievals. Ambient noise was not recorded after one deployment because of a DAT malfunction, but two hours of ambient noise data was recorded during each of the other three deployments. An example of this data is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 5. Test configuration of DDARS at the Ocean Hauldown Facility at NUWCD-AUTEC, Andros, Bahamas.

D. Test Results

In both Fig. 6 and 7 the DDARS omnidirectional sensor and line array measured lower noise levels than the surface deployed omnidirectional hydrophone. Fig. 6 displays the ambient data measured off Andros Island in 1840 m of water. From Fig. 6, it can be seen that the DDARS line array measured 12 dB less noise than the surface hydrophone at 13 kHz, while the single omnidirectional DDARS sensor measured a 6 dB lower level than the surface hydrophone. This indicates that the line array provides an increased SNR equal to these differences. The sea conditions for this test were Sea State 1 with 4-6 kn winds.

The ambient noise measured by the DDARS line array and the single omnidirectional sensor equivalent noise pressure levels are the same at 14 and 16 kHz, respectively, as shown in Fig. 6. However, the equivalent noise pressure of the line array is lower than the single omnidirectional sensor.

Fig. 7 shows the ambient data measured off Eleuthera Island in 4724 m of water. Here, at 13 kHz the line array measured a noise level 18 dB lower than the surface hydrophone, and 8 dB lower than the single DDARS sensor. This data was measured during Sea State 5 conditions with 25-35 kn winds.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The development, test, and evaluation of the DDARS described in this paper were successfully completed and results in the following conclusions and recommendations:

1. The DDARS meets all requirements shown in Table I.
2. The DDARS can be easily deployed and retrieved with a minimum of deck handling equipment. Successful deployments and recoveries were made in Sea States that varied from 1 to 5. The only components too heavy to manually lift are the buoy and anchor.
3. If a high reliability acoustic release with a significantly lower in-water weight can be used, a smaller buoy can be employed which would improve ease of handling for deployment and retrieval.
4. An improved radio transmitter and radio direction finder system should be employed to improve speed and reliability of locating the DDARS on the ocean surface for retrieval.
5. The difference in ambient noise levels measured by the DDARS line array and the single DDARS sensor were small, 6 and 8 dB respectively, indicating the possibility of isotropic deep-ocean ambient noise. Further research is required.

Fig. 6. Ambient noise measured off AUTEc in the Tongue-of-the-Ocean at a depth of 1875 m and wind speed of 4-6 kn; and the equivalent noise pressure levels for both DDARS line array and omnidirectional sensor.

Fig. 7. Ambient noise measured in deep water, 4880 m, off of the northeast coast of Eleuthera Island, Bahamas; wind speed, 25-35 kn.